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Review Article

**REVIEW ON HYPHENATED ANALYTICAL TECHNIQUES
IMPLEMENTED FOR ANALYSIS OF ROSUVASTATIN**¹Atul A. Shirkhedkar, ²Pankaj D. Mahajan, ³Amod S. Patil,¹Department of Pharmaceutical Chemistry, R. C. Patel Institute of Pharmaceutical Education and Research, Shirpur [M.S.], India 425405.**Article Received:** March 2019**Accepted:** April 2019**Published:** May 2019**Abstract:**

Rosuvastatin calcium [RSV] specifically inhibit the enzyme 3-hydroxy-3-methylglutaryl-Co-enzyme A [HMG-CoA] reductase. It belongs to family of cholesterol lowering medications which are denoted as statins and useful in treatment of dyslipidemia where it helps in reducing the chances of atherosclerosis development by decreasing the level of bad cholesterol and hence eliminating the possibilities of heart diseases. RSV was developed by Astra-Zeneca and it was granted approval in 2003 by US-FDA. This article presents a literature review on hyphenated analytical techniques implemented for the estimation of RSV in pharmaceutical preparations and biological fluids.

Keywords: Analytical methods; LC-MS/MS; GC-MS; CE-MS; LC-NMR; Rosuvastatin.**Corresponding author:****Atul A. Shirkhedkar,**

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INTRODUCTION:

Illinois University in the 1950s led to innovation of 3-hydroxy-3-methylglutaryl-CoA [HMG CoA] by the investigators Bimal Kumar Bachhawat and Minor J. Coon, similarly recognized as β -Hydroxy β -methylglutaryl-CoA, which is a transitional in the ketogenesis and mevalonate pathways. It is made by acetoacetyl CoA and acetyl CoA from HMG-CoA synthase[1,2]. HMG-CoA is a transitional metabolic in the metabolism of the amino acid chain, isoleucine, leucine and valine are included[3]. Its immediate precursors are β -hydroxy β -methylbutyryl-CoA [HMB-CoA] and β -methylglutaconyl-CoA [MG-CoA], produces mevalonic acid from HMG-CoA[4-6]. The reductase of HMG-CoA is a cholesterol biosynthesis measurement step. Statins specifically constrain the enzyme 3-hydroxy-3-methylglutaryl - coenzyme A [HMG - CoA], thus preventing the reduction of cholesterol in cardiovascular events[7]. In pharmacokinetics and drug interaction studies, the development of analytical methods for the measuring of statins in biological fluids is a key determinant[8]. To produce reliable pharmacokinetic records, it is essential to use fine - categorized and completely authorized analytical methods. For the quantitation of each HMG-CoA reductase inhibitor, several analytical methods have also been developed in pharmaceutical formulations, which are crucial during the process of quality control of pharmaceutical products. In addition, analytical methods have been developed for the quantification of mevalonate acid to be used as a biomarker for statin inhibition of the enzyme. Statins specifically inhibit the enzyme 3-hydroxy-3-methylglutaryl-coenzyme A [HMG-CoA] hence prevention of cardiovascular events due to the cholesterol reduction[9-12].

The purpose of this review is to provide an overview of relevant published literature and to discuss methods for determining RSV alone or in mixtures, in pure form, formulations and biological samples using the analytical procedure LC – MS / MS.

ROSUVASTATIN CHEMISTRY:

RSV is a synthetic compound produced as monocalcium bis [+] - 7 - [4 - [4 - fluorophenyl] - 6 - isopropyl - 2 - [N - methyl N - methansulfonylamino pyrimidine] - 5 - yl] - [3R, 5S] - dihydroxy - [E] - 6 heptenoate [13, 14]. RSV configuration comprises on its own enantiomer [3R, 5S], expressed and administered as the active hydroxy acid calcium salt [15]. The chemical formula is C₄₄H₅₄CaF₂N₆O₁₂S₂ and molecular weight is 1001.141 g/mol

RSV is a white amorphous powder that is sparingly soluble in methanol [MeOH] and water and slightly soluble in ethanol [EtOH][14,16]. The pharmacophore consists of a portion of dihydroxy heptenoic acid, which binds the target enzyme HMGCoA reductase to the active position[17]. Differently from other statins, the addition of a stable polar methane sulfonamide group in the RSV structure confers relatively low lipophilicity[17,18]. The log D [distribution of the drug into octanol: water] measured at pH 7.4 is -0.33, which is comparable to pravastatin and lower than other statins [atorvastatin, fluvastatin, simvastatin, and cerivastatin][18]. The commercial formulations of RSV tablets available contain 5, 10, 20, or 40 mg of RSV[16].

PHARMACODYNAMICS, EFFICACY, AND SAFETY:

RSV showing effects on lipid profile by inhibiting 3-hydroxy-3-methylglutaryl coenzyme A [HMG-CoA] reductase, a limiting enzyme in cholesterol biosynthesis that liable for conversion of HMG-CoA to mevalonate. RSV is a competitive inhibitor of HMG-CoA reductase, having a chemical structure very similar to HMG portion of HMG-CoA. Olsson et al.[19] have reported that a dosage of RSV starting 1 to 80 mg above 6 weeks has given rise to in LDL - C reductions ranging from 34 percent to 65 percent. There are some reports have been published on effectiveness of RSV over the other statins on reduction of LDL-C[20-22] and it shows that RSV is more effective than other statins in increasing HDL-C and lowering LDL-C at same dose[23]. RSV can be administered along with other drugs to for better management of high-risk patients whose cholesterol level cannot be controlled with RSV monotherapy[24]. In literature it is reported that, RSV showing the adverse effect such as myalgia, myopathy, rhabdomyolysis and acute liver injury[25,26].

PHARMACOKINETICS:

RSV oral bioavailability is about 20 percent and pea plasma concentration [C_{max}] is reached 3-5 hours after 10-80 mg oral dose is given[27]. C_{max} and area under the plasma concentration-time curve [AUC] increase proportionally to the dose. RSV administration with food decreased the ratio of drug absorption by 20 percent as assessed by C_{max}; however the extent of absorption is not affected when measured by AUC[28,29]. The average volume of distribution at steady state of RSV is approximately 134 L. RSV is 88% bound to plasma proteins, mainly albumin. RSV undergoes minimal metabolism with

approximately 10% of radio- labeled dose recovered as metabolite [30-33]. RSV recovery is primarily through fecal elimination route with about 72% of absorbed RSV being eliminated through bile secretion and 28% through renal excretion. The half-life of the circulating plasma is about 20 hours [34]. No effects on RSV pharmacokinetics were observed with deference to age, sex, or daytime [morning or evening] of administration[35,36].

LIQUID CHROMATOGRAPHY-MASS SPECTROMETRY METHODS:

Liquid Chromatography / Mass Spectrometry [LC/MS] is rapidly becoming liquid chromatographers' preferred tool. It's a powerful technique of analysis combining the solving power of LC with mass spectrometry detection specificity[37-39]. Sample components are separated by LC and then introduced to the MS. The MS creates charged ions and detects them. The LC / MS data can be used to deliver information about specific sample components' molecular weight, identity, structure and quantity[40]. LC-MS/MS method is the most explored technique for quantitative analysis of RSV alone or in mixture.

Table 1[41-60] express the LC-MS/MS technique for RSV analysis alone or in mixture with other drugs determined in biological fluids. Most LC-MS/MS analyses were performed in +ve ion mode [ESI+] for the quantification of RSV in human plasma. LC-MS/MS methods were performed with a C18 analytical column and the mobile phase was composed by MeOH or ACN as organic solvent and water with volatile additives including acetate and formic acid, which were added to enhance ionization and increase the method's sensitivity. Multiple reaction monitoring [MRM] was the most commonly used method and the selected [MRM] precursor ion was [M+H+] at m / z 482. RSV can be detected in both +ve and -ve ionization modes of a mass spectrometer, since its structure contains a pyrimidine ring and a carboxylic ring. In order to improve sensitivity, electrospray ionization in the negative mode [ESI-] could be used for MS/ MS detection of RSV in plasma that produced abundant deprotonated molecule [M-H-] at m/z 480 as demonstrated by Gao et al. Retention times were very short, including methods for simultaneous analysis with other drugs, ranging from 0.9 minutes up to 4.1 minutes. Isocratic elution was applied in most cases. More sensitive methods have been developed using LC-MS/MS with linearity ranging from 0.02 ng/mL to 512 ng/mL. A method using LC-MS/MS equipped with an ESI

interface and operated in -ve ionization mode was employed with this aim contrast to the most usual method that uses positive ionization mode for RSV detection. RSV retention time was 4.18 minutes, and the final analysis eluted at 4.95 minutes. Kosek et al. recently reported a sensitive LC - MS / MS method to quantify all statins in human plasma simultaneously. The mass spectrometry was conducted in negative ion electrospray mode for RSV determination and it showed retention time at 3.08 minutes and the lower concentration in the linearity range of 0.4 ng/mL.

Gandla et al. LC - MS / MS technique for RSV resolution in human plasma was studied and certified. RSV d6 has been used as an internal standard [IS]. The method employs lesser plasma volume [100 µL] processed by simple solid-phase extraction [SPE] procedure. This method possesses a suitable degree of precision and accuracy in accordance with US FDA guidelines. The runtime was also set at 2 min, which is fast and more samples can be studied in a day. This analytical method can be obliging for estimating the pharmacokinetics of oral RSV for a pharmacokinetic or bioavailability/bioequivalence studies[41]. **Bai X et al.** has developed rapid and susceptible ultra-performance liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry [UPLC-MS/MS] assay was established and certified for the simultaneous quantification of RSV, RSV-5 S-lactone [RSV-LAC], and N-desmethyl RSV in human plasma. Mass spectrometry detection was performed through positive ion electrospray ionization [ESI][42]. **Kumar et al.** were developed LC-MS / MS technique for simultaneous resolution of RSV and metformin [MET] in human plasma. Simple protein precipitation with acetonitrile [ACN] involved the assay procedure. The portion of supernatant was transferred after precipitation and vaporized under a mild flux of nitrogen [40°C]. The mobile phase residue was reconstituted and injected[43]. **B. Siddartha et al.** has reported the LC-MS/MS method stands validated and is suitable for estimation of plasma RSV concentrations as a single analytical run, in clinical samples from Bioequivalence studies following oral administration of RSV fixed dose [5/10/20mg] tablets in healthy human subjects[44]. **A. Narapusetti et al.** established and certified a rapid, selective and sensitive LC - MS / MS method in MRM mode to determine RSV and amlodipine [AML] in human plasma simultaneously. The proposed technique was fast with a 2.5 min of chromatographic run time and simultaneously suitable for high - performance bioanalysis of RSV and AML. In addition, the method demonstrated suitability for human clinical studies. Furthermore, the sample reanalysis incurred

effectively proves that the assay is reproducible[45]. **Varghese and Ravi** studied simultaneous quantitation of RSV and ezetimibe [EZE] in biological fluid [human plasma] by LC-ESI/MS method Selected ion observing using their particular [M-H] - ions, m/z 480, m/z 408, and m/z 557 respectively for RSV, EZE and Atorvastatin [ATV] as IS was performed on a mass spectrometer. This method was used for pharmacokinetic, bioavailability, or bioequivalent studies of RSV and EZE in human plasma[48]. **R.K. Trivedi et al.** has reported validated LC-MS/MS described herein for the simultaneous estimation of RSV and fenofibric acid [FEA] in human plasma is specific, accurate, precise and reproducible. In addition, the present technique utilizes a single step liquid/ liquid extraction technique with a commercially available IS. The assay was positively applied in a clinical pharmacokinetic study to simultaneously determine the concentration - time profiles of RSV and FEA[59]. **C.K. Hull et al.** has reported sensitive, accurate, reproducible and specific LC-MS/MS technique for the quantification of RSV in human plasma. With a 0.1 ng/ml lower limit of quantification [LLOQ], the desired sensitivity for RSV was achieved. When stored at -220 and -270 ° C, RSV was shown to be stable in routine analytical conditions and human plasma and buffered plasma for up to 6 months. A number of thousands of human plasma samples from a series of human RSV clinical studies were successfully analyzed using the method[60].

CAPILLARY ELECTROPHORESIS-MASS SPECTROSCOPY:

Mohamad Dowod et al. has studied method with the EOF reversal agent, polybrene, in monoammonium carbonate electrolyte, pH 9.00. The ionic power and the quantity of MeOH in buffer were optimized in a multivariate manner use of artificial neural complexes, with optimum conditions being 60mM monoammonium carbonate containing 60 percent MeOH, providing baseline determination within 20 min of the five hypolipidaemics. Using electrokinetic supercharging, the sensitivity of the technique was 1000-fold improved over conventional injections under field-amplified fraction stacking conditions with 180 ng / L LODs. This is the 1st report of CE separation of hypolipidaemics [Pravastatin, Fluvastatin, Atorvastatin, gemfibrozil, Rosuvastatin]. The method was validated and then applicable to the determination of objective drugs in water fractions from Hobart city[61].

GAS CHROMATOGRAPHY-MASS SPECTROSCOPY:

B. H. Woollen et al. has explained study of 3,5-Dihydroxy-3-methylvaleric acid [MVA] in human urine including transformation to MVA lactone [MVAL] and examination by GC-MS. A strategy was explained to achieve a low limit of quantitation to overcome the constraint that calibration must be executed in urine [since MVAL is adsorbed in the absence of matrix] and control urine every time contains significant amounts of MVA. Information are presented for authentication of the technique over the range 75-300 ng mL⁻¹ and for application of the method to a clinical studied with the drug rosuvastatin[62]. **Ali Ismail et al.** determined the residual solvents present in some statins. A selective Gas chromatography with headspace and Mass Spectrometer detectors [HS-GC-MS] has been developed and validated according to different aspect of validation as per ICH. The method has been found to be simple, sensitive, rugged, reliable and reproducible for the quantitation of n-hexane and ethanol widely used during synthesizing of atorvastatin and rosuvastatin or formulating into dosage form. The limit of detection was calculated to be 2.53 ppm and 1.63 ppm per sample for ethanol and n-hexane, respectively. Limit of quantification was 7.59 ppm ethanol, LOQ= 4.89 ppm for n-Hexane. Correlation factor was 0.999 for both ethanol and n-hexane. The percentage recovery was calculated and the value was 99.29 % and 96.01% for ethanol and n-hexane, respectively. The total run is 16 minutes[63].

LIQUID CHROMATOGRAPHY-NUCLEAR MAGNETIC RESONANCE:

Shahu A. et al. studied forced degradation behavior of rosuvastatin under conditions prescribed by ICH. Under acid hydrolytic and photolytic circumstances, the drug was originated to be labile, while base / neutral hydrolytic, oxidative and thermal stress was stable. A total of 11 degradant were prepared, performed on a C-18 column with a stability-indicating technique. LC-MS analyzes specified that five degradation products had the similar molecular mass as the drug, while the remains six had 18 Da less than the drug. Structural elucidation of all the degradant products was performed with the help of sophisticated and modern structural description tools, viz. LC-MS/TOF, LC-MS, on-line H / D exchange and Liquid Chromatography-NMR. The drug's mechanisms of degradation and degradation pathway were delineated. In addition, toxicity in-silico was predicted and equaled with the drug for all degradation products with the help of DEREK and TOPKAT software[64].

CONCLUSIONS:

The present review article gives the comprehensive details about LC-MS/MS, CE-MS, GC-MS, LC-NMR methods applied for the analysis of RSV in pharmaceutical formulation and various biological matrices. Most of these validated hyphenated methods are specific, sensitive, reproducible and accurate. These bioanalytical methods are support to estimation of pharmacokinetic or bioavailability or Bioequivalence studies of oral solid dosage form containing RSV. In this review, the bioanalytical data support the utility of the methods for therapeutic drug monitoring and also for routine chemical sample analysis with desired analogues.

REFERENCES:

1. Debi P. Sarkar [2015]. Classics in Indian Medicine. The National Medical Journal of India [28]: 3. Archived from theoriginal_ on 2016-05-31.
2. Surolia A. An outstanding scientist and a splendid human being: Prof Bimal Kumar Bachhawat. *Glycobiology*. 1997;7[4]:R5-6.
3. Valine, leucine and isoleucine degradation - Reference pathway. Kyoto Encyclopedia of Genes and Genomes. Kanehisa Laboratories. 27 January 2016. Retrieved 1 February 2018.
4. Wilson JM, Fitschen PJ, Campbell B, Wilson GJ, Zanchi N, Taylor L, Wilborn C, Kalman DS, Stout JR, Hoffman JR, Ziegenfuss TN. International society of sports nutrition position stand: beta-hydroxy-beta-methylbutyrate [HMB]. *Journal of the International Society of Sports Nutrition*. 2013 Dec;10[1]:6.
5. Zanchi NE, Gerlinger-Romero F, Guimaraes-Ferreira L, de Siqueira Filho MA, Felitti V, Lira FS, Seelaender M, Lancha AH. HMB supplementation: clinical and athletic performance-related effects and mechanisms of action. *Amino acids*. 2011 Apr 1;40[4]:1015-25.
6. Kohlmeier M. *Nutrient metabolism: structures, functions, and genes*. Academic Press; 2015 May 12.
7. Istvan ES, Deisenhofer J. Structural mechanism for statin inhibition of HMG-CoA reductase. *Science*. 2001 May 11;292[5519]:1160-4.
8. Huang SM, Strong JM, Zhang L, Reynolds KS, Nallani S, Temple R, Abraham S, Habet SA, Baweja RK, Burckart GJ, Chung S. New era in drug interaction evaluation: US Food and Drug Administration update on CYP enzymes, transporters, and the guidance process. *The Journal of clinical pharmacology*. 2008 Jun 1;48[6]:662-70.
9. Jemal M, Schuster A, Whigan DB. Liquid chromatography/tandem mass spectrometry methods for quantitation of mevalonic acid in human plasma and urine: method validation, demonstration of using a surrogate analyte, and demonstration of unacceptable matrix effect in spite of use of a stable isotope analog internal standard. *Rapid Communications in Mass Spectrometry*. 2003 Aug 15;17[15]:1723-34.
10. Wani TA, Samad A, Tandon M, Saini GS, Sharma PL, Pillai KK. The effects of rosuvastatin on the serum cortisol, serum lipid, and serum mevalonic acid levels in the healthy Indian male population. *AAPS PharmSciTech*. 2010 Mar 1;11[1]:425-32.
11. Saini GS, Wani TA, Gautam A, Varshney B, Ahmed T, Rajan KS, Pillai KK, Paliwal JK. Validation of the LC-MS/MS method for the quantification of mevalonic acid in human plasma and determination of the matrix effect. *Journal of lipid research*. 2006 Oct 1;47[10]:2340-5.
12. Saini GS, Wani TA, Ahmed T, Parvez N, Paliwal JK, Pillai KK. Effect of food and rosuvastatin on plasma mevalonic acid levels in male rats. *Ethiopian Pharmaceutical Journal*. 2006;24[1]:59-64.
13. Watanabe M, Koike H, Ishiba T, Okada T, Seo S, Hirai K. Synthesis and biological activity of methanesulfonamide pyrimidine-and N-methanesulfonyl pyrrole-substituted 3, 5-dihydroxy-6-heptenoates, a novel series of HMG-CoA reductase inhibitors. *Bioorganic & medicinal chemistry*. 1997 Feb 1;5[2]:437-44.
14. EP. *European Pharmacopoeia*, 8th edition, Supplement 8.4; EP: Strasbourg, 2015, 4807-09.
15. Chapman MJ, McTaggart F. Optimizing the pharmacology of statins: characteristics of rosuvastatin. *Atherosclerosis Supplements*. 2002 Apr 1;2[4]:33-7.
16. Drugs @ FDA page. Crestor [ROS Calcium, MSD], Astra-Zeneca. https://www.accessdata.fda.gov/drugsatfda_docs/label/2012/.
17. Buckett L, Ballard P, Davidson R, Dunkley C, Martin L, Stafford J, McTaggart F. Selectivity of ZD4522 for inhibition of cholesterol synthesis in hepatic versus non-hepatic cells. *Atherosclerosis*. 2000 Jul 1;151[1]:41.
18. Smith, G.; Davidson, R.; Bloor, S.; Burns, K.; Calnan, C.; McAulay, P.; Torr, N.; Ward, W.; McTaggart, F. *Pharmacological Properties of ZD4522—A New HMG-CoA Reductase Inhibitor*. *Atherosclerosis* 2000, 151, 39, Abstract MoP20:W6.

19. Olsson AG, Pears J, McKellar J, Mizan J, Raza A. Effect of rosuvastatin on low-density lipoprotein cholesterol in patients with hypercholesterolemia. *The American journal of cardiology*. 2001 Sep 1;88[5]:504-8.
20. Brown WV, Bays HE, Hassman DR, McKenney J, Chitra R, Hutchinson H, Miller E, Rosuvastatin Study Group. Efficacy and safety of rosuvastatin compared with pravastatin and simvastatin in patients with hypercholesterolemia: a randomized, double-blind, 52-week trial. *American Heart Journal*. 2002 Dec 1;144[6]:1036-43.
21. Blasetto JW, Stein EA, Brown WV, Chitra R, Raza A. Efficacy of rosuvastatin compared with other statins at selected starting doses in hypercholesterolemic patients and in special population groups. *The American journal of cardiology*. 2003 Mar 6;91[5]:3-10.
22. Jones PH, Davidson MH, Stein EA, Bays HE, McKenney JM, Miller E, Cain VA, Blasetto JW, Group SS. Comparison of the efficacy and safety of rosuvastatin versus atorvastatin, simvastatin, and pravastatin across doses [STELLAR Trial]. *The American journal of cardiology*. 2003 Jul 15;92[2]:152-60.
23. Ballantyne CM, Weiss R, Moccetti T, Vogt A, Eber B, Sosef F, Duffield E, EXPLORER Study Investigators. Efficacy and safety of rosuvastatin 40 mg alone or in combination with ezetimibe in patients at high risk of cardiovascular disease [results from the EXPLORER study]. *The American journal of cardiology*. 2007 Mar 1;99[5]:673-80.
24. Shepherd J, Kastelein JJ, Bittner V, Deedwania P, Breazna A, Dobson S, Wilson DJ, Zuckerman A, Wenger NK. Effect of intensive lipid lowering with atorvastatin on renal function in patients with coronary heart disease: the Treating to New Targets [TNT] study. *Clinical Journal of the American Society of Nephrology*. 2007 Nov 1;2[6]:1131-9.
25. Olsson AG, McTaggart F, Raza A. Rosuvastatin: a highly effective new HMG-CoA reductase inhibitor. *Cardiovascular drug reviews*. 2002 Dec;20[4]:303-28.
26. García-Rodríguez LA, Massó-González EL, Wallander MA, Johansson S. The safety of rosuvastatin in comparison with other statins in over 100 000 statin users in UK primary care. *Pharmacoepidemiology and drug safety*. 2008 Oct;17[10]:943-52.
27. McCormick AD. ZD4522: an HMG-CoA reductase inhibitor free of metabolically mediated drug interactions: metabolic studies in human in vitro systems. *J Clin Pharmacol*. 2000;40:1055.
28. Cooper KJ, Martin PD, Dane AL, Warwick MJ, Raza A, Schneck DW. Lack of effect of ketoconazole on the pharmacokinetics of rosuvastatin in healthy subjects. *British journal of clinical pharmacology*. 2003 Jan;55[1]:94-9.
29. Cooper K, Martin P, Dane A, Warwick M, Schneck D, Cantarini M. The effect of fluconazole on the pharmacokinetics of rosuvastatin. *European journal of clinical pharmacology*. 2002 Nov 1;58[8]:527-31.
30. Martin PD, Dane AL, Nwose OM, Schneck DW, Warwick MJ. No effect of age or gender on the pharmacokinetics of rosuvastatin: a new HMG-CoA reductase inhibitor. *The Journal of Clinical Pharmacology*. 2002 Oct 1;42[10]:1116-21.
31. Martin PD, Mitchell PD, Schneck DW. Pharmacodynamic effects and pharmacokinetics of a new HMG-CoA reductase inhibitor, rosuvastatin, after morning or evening administration in healthy volunteers. *British journal of clinical pharmacology*. 2002 Nov 1;54[5]:472-7.
32. Kitamura S, Maeda K, Wang Y, Sugiyama Y. Involvement of multiple transporters in the hepatobiliary transport of rosuvastatin. *Drug Metabolism and Disposition*. 2008 Oct 1;36[10]:2014-23.
33. Niemi M, Pasanen MK, Neuvonen PJ. Organic anion transporting polypeptide 1B1: a genetically polymorphic transporter of major importance for hepatic drug uptake. *Pharmacological reviews*. 2011 Mar 1;63[1]:157-81.
34. Nozawa T, Nakajima M, Tamai I, Noda K, Nezu JI, Sai Y, Tsuji A, Yokoi T. Genetic polymorphisms of human organic anion transporters OATP-C [SLC21A6] and OATP-B [SLC21A9]: allele frequencies in the Japanese population and functional analysis. *Journal of Pharmacology and Experimental Therapeutics*. 2002 Aug 1;302[2]:804-13.
35. Birmingham BK, Bujac SR, Elsby R, Azumaya CT, Wei C, Chen Y, Mosqueda-Garcia R, Ambrose HJ. Impact of ABCG2 and SLCO1B1 polymorphisms on pharmacokinetics of rosuvastatin, atorvastatin and simvastatin acid in Caucasian and Asian subjects: a class effect. *European journal of clinical pharmacology*. 2015 Mar 1;71[3]:341-55.
36. U.S. Food and Drug Administration. FDA Public Health Advisory for Crestor [ROS], 2005. <https://www.fda.gov/Drugs/DrugSafety/Postmar>

- ketDrugSafetyInformationforPatientsandProvide
rs/ ucm051756.htm
37. Beckett AH and Stenlake GH. Practical Pharmaceutical Chemistry, fourth ed., CBS Publishers and distributors, New Delhi, 2005.
 38. Sharma BK. Instrumental methods of chemical analysis, twenty third ed., Goel Publishing House, Meerut, 2004.
 39. Indian Pharmacopoeia, 1996; 2: A- 67.
 40. Saibaba SV, Kumar MS, Pandiyan PS. MINI REVIEW ON LC/MS TECHNIQUES.2016
 41. Gandla1 K, Repudi L, Kovvasu SP, Raoc RN. Simple and rapid determination of rosuvastatin in human plasma by LC-MS/MS. World journal of pharmacy and pharmaceutical sciences Volume 6, Issue 2011, 1027-1037.
 42. Bai X, Wang XP, He GD, Zhang B, Huang M, Li JL, Zhong SL. Simultaneous Determination of Rosuvastatin, Rosuvastatin-5 S-lactone, and N-desmethyl Rosuvastatin in Human Plasma by UPLC-MS/MS and Its Application to Clinical Study. Drug research. 2017 Dec 12.
 43. Kumar PP, Murthy TE, Rao MB. Development, validation of liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry method for simultaneous determination of rosuvastatin and metformin in human plasma and its application to a pharmacokinetic study. Journal of advanced pharmaceutical technology & research. 2015 Jul;6[3]:118.
 44. Siddartha B, Babu IS. Estimation and validation for determination of rosuvastatin in human plasma by LC/MS/MS method. J. Glob. Trends Pharm. Sci. 2014;5[3]:1979-88.
 45. Narapusetti A, Bethanabhatla SS, Sockalingam A, Repaka N, Saritha V. Simultaneous determination of rosuvastatin and amlodipine in human plasma using tandem mass spectrometry: Application to disposition kinetics. Journal of advanced research. 2015 Nov 1;6[6]:931-40.
 46. Shah Y, Iqbal Z, Ahmad L, Nazir S, Watson DG, Khuda F, Khan A, Khan MI, Khan A, Nasir F. Determination of Rosuvastatin and its Metabolite N-Desmethyl Rosuvastatin in Human Plasma by Liquid Chromatography-High Resolution Mass Spectrometry: Method Development, Validation, and Application to Pharmacokinetic Study. Journal of Liquid Chromatography & Related Technologies. 2015 May 9;38[8]:863-73.
 47. Lee HK, Ho CS, Hu M, Tomlinson B, Wong CK. Development and validation of a sensitive method for simultaneous determination of rosuvastatin and N-desmethyl rosuvastatin in human plasma using liquid chromatography/negative electrospray ionization/tandem mass spectrometry. Biomedical Chromatography. 2013 Nov;27[11]:1369-74.
 48. Varghese SJ, Thengungal Kochupappy R. Development and validation of a liquid chromatography/mass spectrometry method for the simultaneous quantitation of rosuvastatin and ezetimibe in human plasma. Journal of AOAC International. 2013 Mar 1;96[2]:307-12.
 49. Zhang D, Zhang J, Liu X, Wei C, Zhang R, Song H, Yao H, Yuan G, Wang B, Guo R. Validated LC-MS/MS method for the determination of rosuvastatin in human plasma: application to a bioequivalence study in Chinese volunteers. Pharmacology & Pharmacy. 2011 Oct 19;2[04]:341.
 50. Sevda RR, Ravetkar AS, Shirote PJ. UV Spectrophotometric estimation of rosuvastatin calcium and fenofibrate in bulk drug and dosage form using simultaneous equation method. Int. J. Chem. Tech. Res. 2011 Jun;3:629-35.
 51. Macwan JS, Ionita IA, Akhlaghi F. A simple assay for the simultaneous determination of rosuvastatin acid, rosuvastatin-5S-lactone, and N-desmethyl rosuvastatin in human plasma using liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry [LC-MS/MS]. Analytical and bioanalytical chemistry. 2012 Jan 1;402[3]:1217-27.
 52. Hussain S, Patel H, Tan A. Automated liquid-liquid extraction method for high-throughput analysis of rosuvastatin in human EDTA K2 plasma by LC-MS/MS. Bioanalysis. 2009 Jun;1[3]:529-35.
 53. Kallem RR, Karthik A, Chakradhar L, Mullangi R, Srinivas NR. Development and validation of a highly sensitive and robust LC-MS/MS with electrospray ionization method for quantification of rosuvastatin in small volume human plasma samples and its application to a clinical study. Arzneimittelforschung. 2007 Nov;57[11]:705-11.
 54. Gao J, Zhong D, Duan X, Chen X. Liquid chromatography/negative ion electrospray tandem mass spectrometry method for the quantification of rosuvastatin in human plasma: Application to a pharmacokinetic study. Journal of Chromatography B. 2007 Sep 1;856[1-2]:35-40.
 55. Lan K, Jiang X, Li Y, Wang L, Zhou J, Jiang Q, Ye L. Quantitative determination of rosuvastatin in human plasma by ion pair liquid-liquid extraction using liquid chromatography with electrospray ionization tandem mass

- spectrometry. *Journal of pharmaceutical and biomedical analysis*. 2007 Jun 28;44[2]:540-6.
56. Xu DH, Ruan ZR, Zhou Q, Yuan H, Jiang B. Quantitative determination of rosuvastatin in human plasma by liquid chromatography with electrospray ionization tandem mass spectrometry. *Rapid Communications in Mass Spectrometry: An International Journal Devoted to the Rapid Dissemination of Up-to-the-Minute Research in Mass Spectrometry*. 2006 Aug 30;20[16]:2369-75.
57. Oudhoff KA, Sangster T, Thomas E, Wilson ID. Application of microbore HPLC in combination with tandem MS for the quantification of rosuvastatin in human plasma. *Journal of Chromatography B*. 2006 Mar 7;832[2]:191-6.
58. Singh SS, Sharma K, Patel H, Jain M, Shah H, Gupta S, Thakkar P, Patel N, Singh SP, Lohray BB. Estimation of rosuvastatin in human plasma by HPLC tandem mass spectroscopic method and its application to bioequivalence study. *Journal of the Brazilian Chemical Society*. 2005 Oct;16[5]:944-50.
59. Trivedi RK, Kallem RR, Mullangi R, Srinivas NR. Simultaneous determination of rosuvastatin and fenofibric acid in human plasma by LC-MS/MS with electrospray ionization: assay development, validation and application to a clinical study. *Journal of pharmaceutical and biomedical analysis*. 2005 Sep 15;39[3-4]:661-9.
60. Hull CK, Penman AD, Smith CK, Martin PD. Quantification of rosuvastatin in human plasma by automated solid-phase extraction using tandem mass spectrometric detection. *Journal of Chromatography B*. 2002 Jun 5;772[2]:219-28.
61. Dawod M, Breadmore MC, Guijt RM, Haddad PR. Electrokinetic supercharging-electrospray ionisation-mass spectrometry for separation and on-line preconcentration of hypolipidaemic drugs in water samples. *Electrophoresis*. 2010 Apr;31[7]:1184-93.
62. Woollen BH, Holme PC, Martin PD. Development of a sensitive assay for the determination of mevalonic acid in urine and its application to clinical studies with rosuvastatin. *Chromatographia*. 2002 Jan 1;55[1]:S195-6.
63. Ismail A, Alahmad Y. Determination of ethanol and n-hexane residues in bulk rosuvastatin and atorvastatin and their dosage forms using HS-GC-MS developed method. *Research Journal of Pharmacy and Technology*. 2018 Nov 1;11[11]:4829-36.
64. Shah RP, Sahu A, Singh S. LC-MS/TOF, LC-MS n, on-line H/D exchange and LC-NMR studies on rosuvastatin degradation and in silico determination of toxicity of its degradation products: a comprehensive approach during drug development. *Analytical and bioanalytical chemistry*. 2013 Apr 1;405[10]:3215-31.

Figure 1. Chemical structure of rosuvastatin calcium

TABLE 1- LIQUID CHROMATOGRAPHY-MASS SPECTROSCOPY

Drug	Matrices	Interface	Extraction method	Column & Mobile Phase	Flow Rate [ml/min]	Rt [min]	Linearity range	LLOQ	Reference
2017									
RSV	Human plasma	Turboionspray [ESI]	Simple solid phase extraction method, Rosuvastatin d6 as internal standard	Discovery HS C18 [50 mm×4.6 mm, 5µm] column & Ammonium acetate [5mM, pH 3.5]: acetonitrile [20:80, v/v]	0.7	0.85	0.51-100.9 ng/mL	0.51 ng/mL	41
RSV & RSV-LAC & N-Desmethyl RSV	Human plasma	ESI	Liquid-liquid extraction with ethyl acetate from 100 µL acidulated buffered plasma	Acquity UPLC HSS T3 column [100 mm×3.0 mm, 1.8 µm] & 0.1 % gradient formic acid [A]: acetonitrile [solvent B] in gradient elution	0.3	2.69 & 3.10 & 2.33	0.1-50 ng/ml & 0.2-100 ng/ml	0.1 ng/ml & 0.2 ng/ml	42
2015									
RVS & MET	Human plasma	ESI	fortified postextracted sample	Thermo Hypurity C18column [50 mm×4.6 mm, 5 µm] & 0.1% v/v formic acid in water: acetonitrile [30:70 v/v]	0.4	2.01 & 1.43	0.5-200 ng/mL & 2-2000 ng/mL	0.5 ng/mL & 2 ng/mL	43
2014									
RSV	Human plasma	Turboionspray	Solid Phase Extraction; and extracted from human plasma	C18 column [50 mm×4.6 mm, 3 µm] & Acetonitrile: 10 mM ammonium acetate at pH 3.1 [55:45 v/v]	1	1.34	0.5-512 ng/mL	0.5 ng/mL	44

RSV & AML	Human plasma	Turboionspray at 550 °C	Liquid-liquid extraction using a mixture of ethyl acetate and n-hexane [80:20, v/v]	Zorbax SB C18 column [50 mm×4.6 mm, 3.5 µm] & 0.1% formic acid in 5 mM ammonium acetate: methanol: acetonitrile [20:20:60 v/v/v]	0.75	1.30 & 1.7	0.52-51.77 ng/mL & 0.10-10.07 ng/mL	0.52 ng/mL & 0.10 ng/mL	45
RSV & N-Desmethyl RSV	Human plasma	ESI	Liquid-liquid extraction using acetonitrile	HiChrom C18 [150mm×3.0mm, 3 µm] & 0.1% formic acid in acetonitrile: 0.1 % formic acid in water [70:30 v/v]	0.3	3.38 & 2.64	0.2-20 ng/mL & 0.1-10 ng/mL	0.1,0.2 ng/mL & 0.03, 0.1 ng/mL	46
2013									
RSV & N-Desmethyl RSV	Human plasma	ESI	Liquid-liquid extraction using diethyl ether	X-Terra MS C-18 column [50 mm×4.6mm, 5.0 µm] & 15 µmol/L ammonium acetate in water [solution A] and in methanol [Solution B], adjusted to pH 6 with aqueous ammonia [2 mol/L]	0.4	5.061 & 4.226	0.05-42 µg/mL & 0.02-14 ng/mL	0.05 µg/mL & 0.02 µg/mL	47
RSV & EZE	Human plasma	ESI	Liquid-liquid extraction, atorvastatin as internal standard	Luna C18 column [150×4.60 mm, 5 µm] & 0.1% [v/v] formic acid: methanol [20:80 v/v]	1	2.7 & 3.4	0.1-10 ng/mL	0.10 ng/mL	48
2011									
RSV	Human plasma	ESI	Liquid-liquid extraction and solid-phase extraction and extracted with ethyl acetate	Diamonsil C18 column [150 mm×4.6 mm, 5 mm] & Acetonitrile: Methanoic acid [0.1%] [60:40 v/v]	0.8	3.0	0.1-60 ng/mL	0.1 ng/mL	49

RSV	Tablet	ESI	Solid-phase extraction and extracted with methanol	C8 [50 mm×4.6 mm, 5µm] & 0.2% acetic acid: methanol [60:40 v/v]	0.3	6.5	1–6 µg/mL	1 µg/mL	50
RSV & RSV-LAC & N-Desmethyl RSV	Human plasma	ESI	Liquid-liquid and solid-phase extractions and extracted from 50 µL of buffered human plasma by protein precipitation	Zorbax-SB Phenyl column [100 mm×2.1 mm, 3.5 µm] & 0.1% v/v glacial acetic acid in 10% v/v methanol in water [solvent A] and 40% v/v methanol in Acetonitrile [solvent B]	0.35	3.3 & 2.8 & 3.8	0.1-100 ng/mL DM-RSV-0.5-100 µg/mL	0.1 ng/mL DM-RST-0.5	51
2009									
RSV	Human plasma	Turboionspray	Automated liquid-liquid extraction	Symmetry shield RP18 column [50mm×4.6 mm,3.5 µm] & A:Water: methanol [35:65 v/v]; ammonium formate 5mM; B: 100% methanol, gradient elution	1	0.90	50-25000 pg/ml	100 pg/ml	52
2007									
RSV	Human plasma	Turboionspray 475 °C	solid-phase extraction and internal standard from plasma with acetonitrile	Inertsil ODS 3 column [100mm × 4.6mm, 3.0 µm] & 0.05 mol/L formic acid: acetonitrile [20:80 v/v]	0.5	1.8	0.5-50 ng/mL	1 ng/mL	53
RSV	Human plasma	Turboionspray [ESI]	liquid–liquid extraction with ethyl ether	Zorbax XDB-C18 [150mm×4.6mm, 5 µm] column & methanol–water [75:25v/v] adjusted to pH 6 by aqueous ammonia	0.5	2.36	0.02-60 ng/mL	0.02 ng/mL	54

RSV	Human plasma	ESI	Liquid-liquid extraction, Internal standard estrone	Phenomenex Luna C18 5 μ m [150 mm $\times$ 4.6mm] & 2% formic acid: methanol [20:80 v/v]	1	2.3	0.1-20 ng/mL	0.1 ng/mL	55
2006									
RSV	Human plasma	ESI	Liquid-liquid extraction internal standard Cilostazol extracted with ether	Atlantis C18 column [150mm $\times$ 2.1mm, 5.0 μ m] & 0.2% formic acid: methanol [30:70 v/v]	0.2	4.13	0.2-50 ng/mL	0.2 ng/mL	56
RSV	Human plasma	Turboionspray	Solid-phase extraction	Microbore columns packed with Luna C18 [5cm $\times$ 2.0, 1.0 and 0.5 mm]3 μ m & Methanol: water [7:3 v/v] with 0.2% [v/v] formic acid	0.06	1.8	0.05-50 ng/mL	0.05 ng/mL	57
2005									
RSV	Human plasma		Solid phase extraction	YMC J' Sphere ODS H-80 column[150 mm $\times$ 4.6 mm, 4.0 μ m] & 0.2% formic acid in Water: acetonitrile [40: 60 v/v]	1	2.5	1-50 ng/mL	0.25 ng/mL to 100 μ L	58
RSV & FEA	Human plasma	Turboionspray At 400 $^{\circ}$ C	Liquid-liquid extraction, Carbamazepine as internal standard from plasma into ethyl acetate	X-Terra MS C-18 column [50 mm $\times$ 4.6mm, 5.0 μ m] & 0.05M formic acid: acetonitrile [45:55 v/v]	0.4	2.35 & 4.70	1-50 μ g/mL	1 μ g/mL	59
2002									
RSV	Human plasma	Turboionspray	Automated solid-phase extraction	Luna C18 [150 mm $\times$ 4.6 mm,5 μ m] & Methanol: 0.2% formic acid in water [70:30 v/v]	1	3.63	0.1-30 ng/mL	0.1 ng/mL	60

Abbreviation: RSV-LAC: RSV-5S-lactone; MET: metformin; AML: amlodipine; EZE: ezetimibe; FEA: fenofibric acid; ESI: electrospray ionization; Rt: retention time; LLOQ: lower limit of quantification